

Enhancing Intrusion Detection in 5G Networks: A Comparative Study of Generative Adversarial and Diffusion Networks

Pasindu Pamuditha*, Yasodha Gunarathne[†], Sandaru Hettiarachchi[‡],
Charuka Moremada[§], Chamara Sandeepa[¶], Madhusanka Liyanage^{||}

^{*†‡}Department of Electrical and Information Engineering, Faculty of Engineering, University of Ruhuna, Sri Lanka

^{§ ¶||}Network Softwarization and Security Labs (NetsLab), University College Dublin, Ireland

*pasindunadunpamuditha@gmail.com, [†]darshanigunarathne1208@gmail.com, [‡]bhsadaru@gmail.com,

[§]moremada.moremada@ucdconnect.ie, [¶]abeysinghe.sandeepa@ucdconnect.ie, ^{||}madhusanka@ucd.ie

Abstract—With the improvement of 5G Networks, the threat landscape for cyber-attacks has expanded, challenging intrusion detection due to the intelligent and complex nature of the network. Several solutions are emerging to address this issue with Machine Learning (ML)-based Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS). Even though there are implemented IDS ML models, the next problem comes due to a lack of data to accurately train these models. Due to security and privacy restrictions, most organizations are not allowed to use their own data to train a model for intrusion detection. Therefore, in this research, we investigate the generation of tabular network data including malicious data by using Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) and Diffusion Networks for intrusion detection in 5G networks. We aim to enhance the anomaly detection capabilities by combining real and synthetic data. We provide extensive comparison on the performance of GAN and Diffusion models and further explore privacy-preserving techniques. Also, we incorporate Explainable AI (XAI) methods to make explanations for the ML models' predictions on tabular network data.

Index Terms—AI, Machine Learning, XAI, Generative AI, 5G and beyond network Security, NIDS

I. INTRODUCTION

With the expansion of wireless 5G networks, enhancing the speed of network access, lower latency, and high capacity compared to previous generations, new requirements are emerging to ensure networks from potential threats and numerous attack scenarios. Especially, with the accelerated growth of connected IoT with 5G, the number of access points that a network could be exploited has also increased. Furthermore, the ever-increasing use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) has made it easier to launch more intelligent forms of attacks, which can be difficult to be detected by network intrusion detection services. The adversaries will be benefitted from the lack of up-to-date information on such threats that conventional systems rely on.

Therefore, adoption of ML for observing the anomalies and to perform automated intrusion detection is progressing as a method to identify and handle these threats over these complex network infrastructure. However, the Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS) ML models typically require a massive amount of readily-available data to achieve the expectations of highly accurate threat detection. [1] discusses the need for extensive data to train machine learning models for intrusion detection

with high accuracy. Yet, it is infeasible to record such large amounts of data records, as the real adversaries may launch the attacks in short periods or many attack attempts may go unnoticed and not being recorded. Although a large amount of network traffic can be recorded, most of them are benign, which means that a majority of traffic flows are normal and attacks occur rarely. In this case, the lack of malicious data is the problem since we need a sufficient amount of data for every category in model training. It is also expensive to replicate attacks these threats may be emerging from thousands or millions of devices, which makes it infeasible to realistically re-create such attack scenarios to collect data.

As a solution, in this research, we have studied the possibility of applying Generative AI techniques like GANs and Diffusion Networks to generate new malicious types of data to populate those categories. We observe that the current intrusion detection mechanisms rely mainly on real data and do not harness the benefits of these emerging generative AI-based information. Generating malicious data that closely resembles the real data for attack scenarios will solve the lack of data problems and improve the IDS ML model threat detection, even for rare types of attacks. Furthermore, we also implement XAI techniques to enhance the IDS models' interpretability to assess the key improvements from enrichment of data.

A. Our Contributions

Our key contributions are highlighted as follows:

- We provide a novel and comprehensive comparison of the malicious network flow data generated using both GANs and Diffusion Networks, showing their evaluation and effectiveness in ML model training.
- A new approach is developed to enrich the ML models for IDS with the generated malicious network flow data by using GANs and Diffusion Networks. This supports in enhancing the overall detectability in IDS ML applications.
- The generated data are evaluated alongside actual network data by using direct evaluation matrices to check the realistic nature of the synthetic data.
- ML models were trained using both synthetic and real data to evaluate the impact of synthetic data on model

accuracy. By comparing models trained on synthetic versus real data, the evaluation is focused on key metrics to highlight the effectiveness and accuracy of synthetic data.

- XAI technique SHAP was applied for further verification of the similarity of synthetic data to real data via evidences from model output feature attributions.

The rest of the paper is arranged as follows: The background of our work is organized in Section II. Section III provides related works in our paper. Section IV provides the experiment details. Results obtained in each step are explained in Section V. Finally, our conclusions are stated in Section VI.

II. BACKGROUND

A. GANs

The architecture of GAN includes a generator and a discriminator. Here, the generator generates new data and the discriminator attempts to identify the generated data. Through an adversarial process, the generator learns to deceive the discriminator by generating more realistic data.

B. Diffusion Networks

Diffusion models use an alternative approach to generate data. At the training phase, they add a random noise to the input data until the input data is converted into a random noise. This is called forward diffusion. Using this noisy input, the model learns to get the original output data by removing the added noise. This is called backward diffusion. After training, the model can take any random noise and convert it into data that closely resembles the original training data.

C. Methods to asses the statistical similarity of synthetic vs. real data

To evaluate the quality of generated data, we use multiple metrics: Cumulative Distribution Function (CDF), KL divergence and Chi-Squared test. They are used to assess the statistical similarity between real and synthetic data. Each of these methods assesses a different dimension of the statistical similarity of synthetic data. CDF provides a visual distribution check, KL divergence measures the quantifies similarity and Chi-Squared test measures the categorical consistency. These methods provide insights into how closely the synthetic data follows the statistical characteristics of the real data distribution.

1) *Cumulative Distribution Function*: In CDF, we draw a graph that visually compares the cumulative probability, which is a measure of the probability that a random variable will take a value less than or equal to a specific numerical feature. If the plot of synthetic data in CDF follows the plot of real data, it demonstrates high realism.

2) *KL-Divergence*: It is a non-symmetric measure of how two probability distributions diverge from each other. A smaller KL-divergence value indicates greater similarity between the two distributions; the real data and the synthetic data.

It can be calculated as:

$$KL(p||q) = \sum_{i=1}^N p_i \cdot \log \left(\frac{p_i}{q_i} \right) \quad (1)$$

where p is the true probability distribution and q is the approximate probability distribution.

3) *Chi-Squared Test*: For categorical features, the Chi-Squared Test was applied to measure whether there is a statistical relationship between real and synthetic data. A p-value is computed where having p-values greater than 0.05 suggests that the synthetic data has properties similar to the real data. The p-value is a measure of the probability that the observed difference between the expected and observed frequencies in the data.

D. SHAP

A trained ML model is considered a *black box*, which means that it is difficult to understand the reasoning behind why the model provides a particular output. SHapley Additive explanation (SHAP) is a post-hoc XAI technique that supports understanding the outputs of an AI model after training. SHAP leverages game theory to explain the output given by any machine learning model. Commonly, SHAP is used to explain feature contribution for both individual and multiple predictions of models.

III. RELATED WORK

In this section, we discuss previous works related to generating synthetic tabular data using GANs and Diffusion Networks.

TABLE I: Contribution of our work

Description of work	BEGAN [2]	GAN-IDS [3]	SynGAN [4]	NetDiffus [5]	XAI-IDS [6]	Our Work
5G network data analysis						✓
GAN generated data analysis	✓		✓	✓		✓
Diffusion generated data analysis	✓		✓	✓		✓
Real vs. generated data comparison	✓		✓			✓
ML model comparison		✓	✓	✓		✓
XAI based analysis				✓	✓	✓

A. Generate tabular data using GANs

Various techniques are available to generate synthetic tabular data using GANs. For example, in 2014, authors in [7] introduced GANs. They used Generator and Discriminator neural networks to generate images. By following the original GAN architecture, Tabular GANs (TGANs) were introduced to generate tabular data [8]. Then, the work in [9] introduced an improved version to generate tabular data, which is named Conditional Tabular GANs (CTGAN). It outperformed the TGAN method according to the experiments done in [10] where the authors compared the results obtained by TGAN and CTGAN for EEG data. Another method for tabular data

generation was introduced in [2] named BEGAN which incorporated the auto-encoder model as the discriminator. Here, synthetic data generation was done for various attack types including DoS, Probe, and Reconnaissance, and demonstrated the ML models trained with the combination of real and synthetic data predicted high accuracy.

Although such ML models are trained using GAN synthetic malicious data, the state of the art solutions lack extensive performance and quality evaluation of synthetic data for IDS. Evaluating synthetic malicious data with the real dataset via evaluation matrices helps to understand its realistic nature more effectively for the IDS applications to achieve high detectability over real threats.

B. Generate tabular data using Diffusion Networks

Diffusion networks were first introduced to generate image data in [11]. To generate tabular data from diffusion models, TabDDPM was introduced. The authors in [12] used TabDDPM to generate financial data. The work presented in [13] use diffusion methods as an imputation technique. However, limited work has been done in the area of generating tabular network and IDS related data via Diffusion networks. Therefore, we provide a comprehensive analysis on the applicability of diffusion networks for data generation in IDS ML applications.

IV. METHODOLOGY

A. System Model

Fig. 1: System Model

Fig. 1 illustrates the system model of our proposed data generation and analysis process. Synthetic data are generated using Generative AI models such as GAN and Diffusion Networks by applying real malicious data in scenarios like DoS Attacks, DDoS Attacks, and Port Scan Attacks. Synthetic malicious data are used to train four ML models integrating with real data. Each model is trained in multiple stages by varying the proportions of real and synthetic data. Moreover, SHAP is applied for data and prediction explanation.

B. Dataset Selection

We select 5G-NIDD dataset [14] as the primary dataset, which is a recent IDS dataset on a real 5G test network. Table IIa shows the count of each attack type and benign data in the dataset. It includes 52 features with 32 float, 12 int, and 8 categorical types. It consists of 1215890 records including

477737 benign data and 738153 malicious data with eight different attack types.

TABLE II: Distribution of Attacks in Malicious Records and Feature Scores

(a) Distribution of Attacks types			(b) ANOVA F-scores	
Label	records	Percentage	Feature	Score
UDPFlood	457340	61.96%	Seq	329,589.08
HTTPFlood	140812	19.08%	Offset	223,791.80
SlowrateDos	73124	9.91%	sTtl	189,934.06
TCPConnectScan	20052	2.72%	e	159,060.91
SYNScan	20043	2.72%	tcp	142,813.28
UDPScan	15906	2.15%	AckDat	80,707.00
SYNFlood	9721	1.32%	RST	35,379.19
ICMPFlood	1155	0.16%	INT	33,941.29
Total	738153	100.00%	TcpRtt	32,500.88
			icmp	29,713.08

The rows with null values were dropped to ensure that our dataset is free from incomplete data points, and feature selection was done using Pearson correlation matrix and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA F- Score).

1) *Pearson correlation matrix*: Pearson correlation matrix is used to identify highly correlated features that have the same contribution for the target variable. If there are any, one feature from those two features is dropped ensuring no redundant features in the dataset.

2) *ANOVA F-score*: As the next step of our feature selection process, the ANOVA F-Score method was applied to select top features. It filters top features that mostly contribute to the classification task.

Finally, the top 23 features were selected for this research. Among them, the top 10 features are shown in Table II b.

C. Data Generation

1) *Data Generation using GANs*: We implemented CTGAN for synthesizing tabular data using PyTorch [9]. Here, the generator transforms random noise into synthetic data using three fully connected layers with ReLU activations. It has residual layers such that the data synthesis is performed correctly with help from a linear layer to align data dimensions. The Discriminator utilizes several linear layers with LeakyReLU activation and Dropout. It differentiates real from synthetic data to give an output probability by a Sigmoid function. The CTGAN class coordinates the training with a DataTransformer for pre-processing and a DataSampler for conditional vector generation.

2) *Data Generation using Diffusion Networks*: As the next approach, TabDDPM is used, a version of Diffusion models optimized for tabular data generation. Number of neurons in the input layer and output layer is equivalent to the number of features in the dataset. There are 128 neurons in the hidden layers. These layers are connected with the ReLU activation function to introduce the nonlinearity to the model.

For each of the attack types, synthetic data were generated separately. Finally, we combined these datasets together and created two datasets for the experiments: GAN-generated dataset, and the Diffusion-generated dataset.

D. Synthetic Data Evaluation

We use numerous evaluation metrics to evaluate the realism and effectiveness of synthetic data, including Cumulative Distribution Function, KL-Divergence, Cosine Distance, and Chi-Squared test.

E. Data Pre-processing and Model Training

In our work, four ML models were trained using these datasets generated by both Diffusion Networks and GAN and combined with the real 5G-NIDD dataset. We used Decision Tree, Random Forest, K-Nearest Neighbour (KNN) and Support Vector Machine (SVM) as the ML models. Each model was trained in multiple stages by varying the used proportions of real and synthetic data in following proportions:

- 100% real data
- 20% real data and 80% synthetic data.
- 50% real data and 50% synthetic data.
- 80% real data and 20% synthetic data.

The performance evaluation of these models was done using various metrics such as F1-Score, Precision, Recall, Training Accuracy, and Testing Accuracy to determine the effectiveness of the synthetic data in replacing the real data.

F. Application of XAI Methods

In this work, the SHAP XAI method is applied to all trained models to visualize the feature importance of the model’s predictions. In this research, several SHAP plots have been used to visualize the feature importance for a particular prediction such as the Waterfall plot, Force plot, Stacked force plot, Beeswarm Summary plot, and Mean SHAP plot.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Performance Evaluation for GAN and Diffusion Network Generated Data

1) *Cumulative Distribution Results:* Fig. 2 shows the CDF graphs for generated data by using GANs and Diffusion Networks. Here, we can observe that data generated using GANs is closer to real data than data generated from Diffusion Networks. In “Seq”, “REQ”, “Offset”, “INT”, “Mean” and “Status”, the CDF graphs of GAN generated data are closely aligned with the real data but the Diffusion Network-generated data has more divergence in those results. GANs have an adversarial training process, which allows the generator to improve by competing against the discriminator. This iterative improvement enables GANs to generate synthetic data that follows real data distribution. Therefore, according to these results, GAN-data can capture more complex statistical properties of the real data.

2) *KL-Divergence Results:* Table III shows the KL Divergence values for synthetic data generated by using GANs and Diffusion Networks. The results also indicate that GAN data is better than the Diffusion Network-based data. The variation in KL Divergence values for GANs and Diffusion models arises from differences in how these models approximate the real data distribution. KL Divergence values for GANs are

Fig. 2: Cumulative distribution of generated data vs real data

very low (0.0000 for UDPFlood and ICMPFlood, 0.0001 for UDPScan). As Diffusion Networks rely on a more complex denoising process, it may not always capture the complexity of real data. The higher KL Divergence values for Diffusion Networks (0.7696 for SYN Flood, 0.5328 for TCPConnectScan) suggest that Diffusion generated data struggle to perfectly reverse the noise process in a way that follows the real data distribution.

TABLE III: KL divergence results

	UDP Flood	TCP Connect Scan	UDP Scan	SYN Flood	ICMP Flood
GAN	0.0000	0.0168	0.0001	0.0278	0.0000
Diffusion	0.1117	0.5328	0.0815	0.7696	0.0036

3) *Chi-Squared Test Results:* Table V illustrates the calculated Chi-Squared test p-values for three attack types based on five features. If the p-value is greater than 0.05, it indicates that synthetic data is statistically similar to the real data. According to the results obtained in this experiment, the GAN generated data shows p-values that are close to 1.0000 for all features across all attack types. In contrast, the Diffusion network generated data shows p-values (≈ 0.4914) less than 0.05 for most of the features across all attack types. Overall, GAN consistently achieved perfect p-values outperforming Diffusion Network across all features. It demonstrates that synthetic data of GAN is statistically similar to the real data rather than the Diffusion Networks. As Diffusion Networks generate data gradually by adding and removing noise, it is more suitable for producing continuous data than categorical features due to the less effectiveness of capturing discrete variables.

B. Performance Evaluation of Models Trained with GAN and Diffusion Network Generated Data Integrating Real Data

1) *Confusion Matrix:* Confusion Matrices were plotted for all the models trained with different percentages of synthetic data integrated with real data. Fig. 3a, Fig. 3b and Fig. 3c

Fig. 3: Confusion Matrix for Random Forest models trained with different proportions of real and generated data

TABLE IV: Performance Comparison of Models with GAN, Diffusion, and Real Data

Model	Matrices	20%		50%		80%		100% Real Data
		GAN	Diffusion	GAN	Diffusion	GAN	Diffusion	
Decision Tree	Training Accuracy	99.90%	99.80%	99.87%	99.86%	99.81%	99.74%	99.93%
	Testing Accuracy	99.80%	99.80%	99.52%	99.46%	98.36%	98.88%	99.93%
	F1-Score	99.80%	99.79%	99.52%	99.45%	98.35%	98.87%	99.93%
Random Forest	Training Accuracy	99.28%	98.48%	99.17%	98.48%	99.11%	99.50%	99.93%
	Testing Accuracy	99.22%	98.74%	99.14%	98.12%	98.44%	97.44%	99.93%
	F1-Score	99.18%	98.41%	99.10%	97.91%	98.41%	97.28%	99.93%
KNN	Training Accuracy	85.94%	91.24%	77.74%	88.82%	73.61%	89.24%	93.86%
	Testing Accuracy	84.44%	85.28%	75.14%	75.14%	63.38%	64.80%	93.86%
	F1-Score	84.58%	85.50%	76.47%	75.97%	66.64%	67.02%	93.66%
SVM	Training Accuracy	97.14%	84.04%	96.76%	81.98%	96.58%	90.32%	98.31%
	Testing Accuracy	98.32%	86.56%	97.46%	67.12%	95.08%	65.78%	98.31%
	F1-Score	98.33%	81.05%	97.48%	61.51%	95.23%	59.66%	98.31%

TABLE V: Chi-Squared Test Results

Features	TCPConnectScan		SYNScan		UDPScan	
	GAN	Diff	GAN	Diff	GAN	Diff
RST	1.000	0.491	0.668	0.491	0.849	0.489
CON	1.000	0.491	1.000	0.491	1.000	0.489
tcp	1.000	0.481	1.000	0.435	1.000	0.489
dMeanPktSz	0.999	0.489	1.000	0.489	0.808	0.488
icmp	1.000	0.491	1.000	0.491	0.942	0.489

compares the model performance of Random Forest classifier models trained on 100% real data and 80% of 80% synthetic (GAN and Diffusion Network) with 20% real data. It seems there is no any significant difference among them. Overall, all plots demonstrate better performance, especially in classifying "Benign", "HTTPFlood", "UDPFlood" and "SlowrateDos" traffic. This indicates that synthetic data can be effectively used to train ML models while maintaining accurate predictions.

2) *F1-Score*: Table IV highlights the results of F1-Score values calculated with the blend of Precision and Recall. Decision Tree and Random Forest: Both models keep their performance in F1-Score values above 95% with both GAN and Diffusion Network synthetic data, only slightly decreasing as the proportion of synthetic data increases. However, the reliability of models with synthetic data is inconsistent overall.

KNN significantly performs worse than other models, especially with GAN data, getting poorer as synthetic data increases. However, it performs better with Diffusion Network data at low synthetic data proportions but is still inconsistent

overall. When considering the SVM model, it performs well with GAN generated data showing high FI-Score values above 95%. It is very inconsistent for Diffusion Network data, especially at higher synthetic data percentages where performance drops sharply.

3) *Training and Testing Accuracy*: The comparison in Table IV demonstrates the consistent outer performance of Decision Tree and Random Forest over KNN and SVM in both training and testing accuracy. Decision Tree and Random Forest maintain superior performance in accuracy across all models that are trained on different proportions (20%, 50%, 80%) of both GAN and Diffusion, but the models that are trained with GAN slightly perform better overall. Testing accuracy is lower for KNN and SVM when training with a high proportion of synthetic data, especially Diffusion-generated data. Overall, GAN outperforms Diffusion in the performance for testing accuracy.

C. Application of SHAP for Model Prediction Explanations

SHAP values for the trained Random Forest ML model with 100% real data, 80% GAN generated data, and 80% Diffusion Network generated data, are visualized in a Beeswarm plot in Fig. 4 highlighting how each feature contributes to the prediction in "UDPFlood" attack type. It ranks features for each value of importance in the SHAP values. Here, Feature values are represented by color and jittered points indicate the distribution of SHAP values. The features which show the

Fig. 4: SHAP Beeswarm Plots for models trained with different proportions of real and generated data

highest contribution in the prediction of the model with 100% real data could maintain their contribution in both models trained with 80% GAN and 80% Diffusion Network synthetic data. The "Seq" variable has a high negative contribution when its values are high. The "tcp" and "sMeanPktSz" variables have high positive contributions when their values are low in all plots. However, the features (SMeanPktSz, Offset, STtl, tcp, SHops) demonstrate consistent positive contributions with their various low values in all datasets. Also, the features (tcp, sHops, Seq) demonstrate consistent negative contributions with their various high values in all datasets. These results suggest that the same set of major features have been identified by both generation processes.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this research, we explore the possibilities of generating tabular data using generative AI techniques and how those data can improve NIDS. We identified that GAN and Diffusion both can be used to generate network flows to address the shortage of malicious data in intrusion detection. Despite the differences, it is possible to generate synthetic data by using CTGAN and TabDDPM with similar properties to real data. However, GAN generated data are closer to real data distributions capturing most of the correlations compared to diffusion-based data generation. Our results show that Random forest performs better as a ML model to detect malicious data among the tested models across different evaluation metrics. Furthermore, the XAI technique SHAP enables the observation of key features that make minor variations across real and generated data.

The limitations observed in the Diffusion model in being able to encode complex data patterns can be addressed in future work with hybrid models combining the adversarial training of GANs with Diffusion Networks. Furthermore, extensions of the XAI techniques beyond SHAP (for instance, adoption of LIME or TreeExplainer) may uncover additional insights in feature importance and facilitate more understanding of the models in practical uses. A set of further experiments with different synthetic-to-real data ratios could also contribute to achieving optimal accuracy for intrusion detection systems.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work is partly supported by the European Union under the ENSURE-6G project (Grant Agreement No. 101182933) and CONNECT phase 2 project by Research Ireland (Grant no. 13/RC/2077_P2).

REFERENCES

- [1] N. Shone, T. N. Ngoc, V. D. Phai, and Q. Shi, "A deep learning approach to network intrusion detection," *IEEE Transactions on Emerging Topics in Computational Intelligence*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 41–50, 2018.
- [2] C. Park, J. Lee, Y. Kim, J.-G. Park, H. Kim, and D. Hong, "An enhanced ai-based network intrusion detection system using generative adversarial networks," *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, vol. 10, no. 3, pp. 2330–2345, 2023.
- [3] J. Lee and K. Park, "GAN-based imbalanced data intrusion detection system," *Personal and Ubiquitous Computing*, vol. 25, pp. 121–128, 11 2019.
- [4] J. Charlier, A. Singh, G. Ormazabal, R. State, and H. Schulzrinne, "Syngan: Towards generating synthetic network attacks using gans," 08 2019.
- [5] N. Sivaroopan, D. Bandara, C. Madarasingha, G. Jourjon, A. P. Jayasumana, and K. Thilakarathna, "Netdiffus: Network traffic generation by diffusion models through time-series imaging," *Computer Networks*, vol. 251, p. 110616, 2024.
- [6] B. Mahbooba, M. Timilsina, R. Sahal, and M. Serrano, "Explainable artificial intelligence (xai) to enhance trust management in intrusion detection systems using decision tree model," *Complexity*, vol. 2021, no. 1, p. 6634811, 2021.
- [7] I. Goodfellow, J. Pouget-Abadie, M. Mirza, B. Xu, D. Warde-Farley, S. Ozair, A. Courville, and Y. Bengio, "Generative adversarial nets," in *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems* (Z. Ghahramani, M. Welling, C. Cortes, N. Lawrence, and K. Weinberger, eds.), vol. 27, Curran Associates, Inc., 2014.
- [8] L. Xu and K. Veeramachaneni, "Synthesizing tabular data using generative adversarial networks," 2018.
- [9] L. Xu, M. Skoularidou, A. Cuesta-Infante, and K. Veeramachaneni, "Modeling tabular data using conditional gan," 2019.
- [10] M. Cheon, H. Dong, J. Lee, Park, H. Choi, J. Lee, and O. Lee, "Ctgan vs tgan? which one is more suitable for generating synthetic eeg data," vol. 99, 05 2021.
- [11] J. Ho, A. Jain, and P. Abbeel, "Denosing diffusion probabilistic models," in *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems* (H. Larochelle, M. Ranzato, R. Hadsell, M. Balcan, and H. Lin, eds.), vol. 33, pp. 6840–6851, Curran Associates, Inc., 2020.
- [12] T. Sattarov, M. Schreyer, and D. Borth, "Findiff: Diffusion models for financial tabular data generation," in *Proceedings of the Fourth ACM International Conference on AI in Finance*, ICAIF '23, (New York, NY, USA), p. 64–72, Association for Computing Machinery, 2023.
- [13] M. Villaizán-Valledado, M. Salvatori, C. Segura, and I. Arapakis, "Diffusion models for tabular data imputation and synthetic data generation," 07 2024.
- [14] S. Samarakoon, Y. Siriwardhana, P. Porambage, M. Liyanage, S.-Y. Chang, J. Kim, J. Kim, and M. Ylianttila, "5g-nidd: A comprehensive network intrusion detection dataset generated over 5g wireless network," 2022.